

AFT samples source	Refraction_profiles	— UIB_SV_79-line	— NH8509_CMP.kml-line
● Blythe & Kleinspehn, 1998	— Refraction_profiles	— UIB_SVA_87-line	ST
● Dorr et al, 2012	— OBS2008.kmz-line	NPD	— ST8515-line
● Dorr et al, 2019a	● OBS_20130200	— NPD_MOFF_97-line	— ST8414-line
● Dorr et al, 2019b	● 99400-stations	— NPD_MOFF_93-line	Others
● Meier et al, 2024	● 99300-stations	— NPD_MOFF_90-line	— NPI_BEL_87-line
● Schaaf et al, 2021	● 99200-stations	— NPD_MOFF_89-line	— NP_IS_85-line
NGU Geophysical_data	● 97260-stations	SVA	— MS87_SVA.kml-line
— Airborne_gravity_SAG-98-99	— Czuba2005_OBS_line.kmz-line	— SVA_VM_85-line	● Earthquakes_1980-2012
● GroundGravity_2022	Offshore seismic	— SVA_FO_85-line	● Earthquakes_2012-2023
— Marine_Gravity	UiB	— SVA_IS_85-line	
Other geophysical data	— UIB_SV_76-line	NH	
● GNSS-stations-SVA	— UIB_SV_77-line	— NH8509-line	

SVALGEOLOG:
Map of compiled geological and geophysical data
 Background map from © Norwegian Polar Institute (npolar.no)

WGS 84 / UTM zone 33N
 EPSG: 32633

0 20 40 60 km